

NEWSLETTER -Vol.2-

SITE VISIT

NanoBio4Can Team Visits Trustlife

A collaborative open access review article led by Kashif Maroof, PhD a NanoBio4Can MSCA Cofund Postdoctoral Programme Fellow, under the supervision of Rükân Genç Altürk, PhD, and co-authored with Ronald Fook Seng Lee, PhD and Pinar Karacabey, has been published in ACS Pharmacology & Translational Science.

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WEBINAR SERIES

The NanoBio4Can Webinar Series Continues with Third Webinar on June 4

As part of the NanoBio4Can Program, the “NanoBio4Can Monthly Webinar Series,” where postdoctoral researchers share insights into their scientific work, was held on June 4, 2026. Organized within the framework of the dissemination and communication activities of the MSCA COFUND Grant Agreement, the webinar provided an opportunity for researchers to present their work and engage with colleagues as well as researchers interested in the topic.

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NEW COMERS

New MSCA Cofund Fellows join NanoBio4Can

New fellows bring fresh expertise to NanoBio4Can's international research network in nanobiotechnology.

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TRAINING

Theoretical and Hands-on Training

On Thursday, March 26, 2026, a theoretical and hands-on training session was organized at the SUNUM infrastructure for conventional PCR, quantitative PCR (qPCR), and Droplet Digital PCR (ddPCR) systems. The training, to which all current and potential users of the equipment were invited, was delivered by SUNUM Technical Staff Halit Yusuf Altay. Participants had the opportunity to perform hands-on practice at the instruments as part of the training.

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NanoBio4Can Workshop at SUNUM

SUNUM hosted a one-day workshop entitled “Advanced Electron Microscopy in Drug Delivery Systems” on April 16, 2026 for NanoBio4Can MSCA Cofund fellows.

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Sterile Techniques Training

On Thursday, March 26, 2026, a theoretical and hands-on training session was organized at the SUNUM infrastructure for conventional PCR, quantitative PCR (qPCR), and Droplet Digital PCR (ddPCR) systems. The training, to which all current and potential users of the equipment were invited, was delivered by SUNUM Technical Staff Halit Yusuf Altay. Participants had the opportunity to perform hands-on practice at the instruments as part of the training.

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UP COMING

The NanoBio4Can Webinar Series Continues with Forth Webinar on June 30

As part of the NanoBio4Can Program, the “NanoBio4Can Monthly Webinar Series,” where postdoctoral researchers will share information about their scientific work, continues on Tuesday, June 30, 2026. Organized as part of the dissemination and communication activities under the MSCA COFUND Grant Agreement, these webinars will provide researchers with the opportunity to share their research with both colleagues and researchers interested in the topic.

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